

COMPLEX COMPOUNDS OF BIGUANIDE WITH BIVALENT METALS. PART II. NICKEL BIGUANIDINES.

BY PRIYADARANJAN RÂY AND BHUPESH CHANDRA PURAKAYASTHA.

Nickel bisbiguanide dihydrate, which was also isolated by earlier workers, has been prepared and found to behave as a diacidic base in all its compounds. This has been found to lose water at 110° and form the anhydrous base Ni (C₂N₆H₈)₂. Like the corresponding chromium, cobalt and copper compounds, previously described, it also forms a special type of inner metallic complex of the second order

A series of salts of the base with simple and complex anions, including polyiodides, has been prepared and their properties studied. These are, namely, chloride, bromide iodide, fluoride, double acid fluoride, chlorate, bromate, iodate, periodate, perchlorate, permanganate, borofluoride, nitrate, nitrite, sulphite, thiosulphate, dithionate, thiocyanate, selenate, chromate, carbonate, ferrocyanide, ferricyanide, nitroprusside, cobalticyanide, cobaltinitrite, mercuri-iodide, iodo-tri-iodide and chloro-tri-iodide. They resemble the corresponding copper compounds in many respects.

In Part I of this series a study of the preparation and properties of copper biguanidine and its various salts has been reported (Rây and Bagchi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **16**, 617). References to the earlier work on complex compounds of biguanide and its substitution products with bivalent metals like copper, nickel and cobalt have also been given there. A complete discussion on the constitution of these compounds will be found in a previous paper by one of us (Rây and Saha, *ibid.*, 1937, **14**, 670). A study of the preparation and properties of the corresponding nickel biguanidine and its salts forms the subject of the present communication.

Of the various compounds studied, the hydrated base and the sulphate were described by earlier workers (*cf.* Friedrich, *Monatsh*, 1883, **4**, 888 ; Stumpf, "Dissertation", Berlin, 1934, p. 48).

It has been observed that the salts of the base with bivalent simple anions are practically insoluble or sparingly soluble, whereas those with simple monovalent anions are generally soluble in water, the case of acid double fluoride, nitrate, iodate and periodate being exceptional. The last one has, however, behaved as a tribasic acid in the compound isolated. It has been further observed that no derivatives with mixed acid anions are formed in the case of simple univalent or bivalent anions.

Among the salts of the complex acids studied, none with mixed anions were found to be formed with dibasic and tetrabasic acids. But in the case of tri- and mono-basic complex acids, two series of salts, the normal and the

mixed, were obtained. The complex base also forms aurichloride and sparingly soluble platinichloride resembling those of organic bases.

It may further be mentioned that similarity in properties, as regards solubility and water of crystallisation, has been observed in the following groups of salts:—sulphate, chromate and selenate; nitrate and chlorate; ferricyanide and cobalticyanide. Perchlorate, permanganate and borofluoride have been found to be anhydrous and of the same crystalline shape. Besides, the nickel biguanide complexes closely resemble the corresponding copper compounds in solubility and often in containing the same number of water molecules in the crystal. These facts are in perfect accord with the isomorphous relations known among the members of each group and suggest similar relationship between the corresponding nickel and copper biguanide compounds.

The polyiodide of the complex base also presents an interesting case. Ephraim (*Ber.*, 1921, 54, 379,394) prepared the complex polyiodide of the hexammine compounds of bivalent metals, like nickel, copper, zinc and cadmium, by the action of the corresponding complex chloride on a solution of iodine in potassium iodide. With increasing concentration of iodine he obtained higher polyiodides. But in the present case only one molecule of iodine has been found to combine with one molecule of complex nickel biguanide iodide even with a very large concentration of iodine, though, theoretically, a combination with at least two molecules might have been expected. With an excess of nickel biguanide hydrochloride, on the other hand, a chloro-polyiodide was formed, which, however, changed into the pure iodo-polyiodide when subsequently treated with an excess of potassium tri-iodide solution. Their constitutions are represented by the following formulae:

Iodo-tri-iodide

Chloro-tri-iodide

where $X = Ni (BigH^+)_2$, the nickel biguanide complex cation, $BigH$ representing one molecule of biguanide. These polyiodides in the dry state are quite stable, being unaffected by treatment with carbon disulphide. But the latter solvent can remove the whole of the excess iodine from *moist* polyiodide by repeated extraction. This is evidently due to the dissociation of the polyiodide ion in presence of water, though they are sparingly soluble. Their stability and low solubility might in this case be attributed to the equalisation of ionic volumes by complex formation, which renders possible a close packing to strengthen the crystal lattice.

Finally, both the dihydrate and the anhydrous base have been found to be diamagnetic, which means according to Pauling (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 53, 1367, 3225), that an inner 3-d orbital is involved in the sharing of electrons leading to the formation of the complex (dsp^2 bonds); this gives a planar configuration of the biguanide molecules about the nickel atom.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Nickel bisBiguanidinium Chloride.—A solution of nickel chloride (1 mol.) was added, drop by drop, to a solution of biguanide sulphate (2 mols.) containing an excess of caustic soda. The crude base, mixed with a small amount of nickel hydroxide, was precipitated in the form of yellow, silky crystals. This was digested with semi-normal hydrochloric acid to give a neutral solution, which was filtered and evaporated to a small volume on the water-bath. The solution was kept overnight in the cold when a large crop of long, needle-shaped, orange-yellow crystals separated out. These were washed first with ice-cold water and then with alcohol. For analysis they were dried in air.

The chloride was also prepared by rubbing the powdered base with a concentrated solution of ammonium chloride in a mortar in the cold, when ammonia was displaced from the ammonium chloride by the complex base. {Found: N, 38.03; Cl, 19.40; Ni, 15.97. $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_2\text{N}_5\text{H}_7)_2]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 38.07; Cl, 19.32; Ni, 15.96 per cent.}

Equivalent conductivity at 25°.

v (in litres) =	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024
λ_e	= 81.02	97.88	106.0	111.3	115.2	119.0	123.3
λ_e (mean) =	122.9						

From Walden's formula $\lambda_e = \lambda_0 (1 + n_1 \cdot n_2 \cdot 0.692 v^{-\frac{1}{2}})$, where n_1 and n_2 are the valencies of the cation and the anion (*cf.* Walden, *Leitvermögen der Lösungen*, 1925, V, p. 33).

The mobility of $\frac{1}{2} \text{Ni}(\text{C}_2\text{N}_5\text{H}_7)_2^+ = 122.90 - 76.63 = 46.27$, the ionic mobility of the chlorine ion being 76.63 at 25° (Ferguson and Vogel, *Phil. Mag.*, 1927, iv, 9, 223).

Nickel bisBiguanidinium Hydroxide.—The pure dihydrate was prepared by treating the solution of the complex chloride with that of sodium hydroxide. The silky, yellow, crystalline precipitate was filtered, washed first with water till free from alkali and then with alcohol. The crystals were dried in air free from carbon dioxide.

The substance liberates ammonia from ammonium salts, does not decompose readily when treated with alkali and sodium peroxide, and is

insoluble in organic solvents like alcohol or ether. {Found : N, 47'53 ; Ni, 19'89. $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_2\text{N}_6\text{H}_7)_2](\text{OH})_2$ requires N, 47'50; Ni, 19'92 per cent}.

The magnetic susceptibility of the substance, measured in a Curie's balance at 27° gave $\chi_m = -0'2212 \times 10^{-6}$.

The dihydrate was also prepared by Stumpf (*op. cit.*) by treating nickel biguanide sulphate with potassium hydroxide.

Nickel bisBiguanidine.—The bisbiguanide dihydrate, when heated at 110° for about 10 hours, lost 12'3% of its weight. The calculated value for the water in the dihydrate equals 12'22 per cent. The corresponding copper compound also loses its water at the same temperature (*cf.* Rây and Bagchi, *op. cit.*). {Found : Ni, 22'80. $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_2\text{N}_6\text{H}_6)_2$ requires Ni, 22'70 per cent}.

The anhydro-base is also insoluble in organic solvents like alcohol and ether. It is reddish yellow in colour which changes to yellow on exposure to air with regeneration of the original dihydrate.

Its magnetic susceptibility at 27°, $\chi_m = -0'1491 \times 10^{-6}$.

Nickel bisbiguanidinium bromide was obtained in the form of deep yellow, crystalline precipitate by adding a strong solution of the complex chloride to that of potassium bromide. It was recrystallised from warm water and then washed and dried as described in the case of the chloride. {Found : Br, 35'48 ; Ni, 13'09. $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_2\text{N}_6\text{H}_7)_2]\text{Br}_2 \cdot 1'5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Br, 35'72 ; Ni, 13'11. per cent}.

Nickel bisbiguanidinium iodide prepared like the previous compound from the complex chloride and potassium iodide, was recrystallised from warm water and dried in air. It resembles the corresponding chloride and bromide in properties. {Found : I, 49'44 ; Ni, 11'42. $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_2\text{N}_6\text{H}_7)_2]\text{I}_2$ requires I, 49'33 ; Ni, 11'41 per cent}.

Nickel bisbiguanidinium fluoride separated slowly as orange-yellow crystals when to a concentrated solution of ammonium fluoride, a solution of the complex chloride was added drop by drop. They were recrystallised from water, washed and dried as usual. {Found : F, 9'86 ; Ni, 15'48. $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_2\text{N}_6\text{H}_7)_2]\text{F}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires F, 10'01 ; Ni, 15'46 per cent .

Nickel bisbiguanidinium ammonium acid fluoride was obtained as a light brown precipitate when a concentrated solution of ammonium acid fluoride was treated with that of nickel biguanide chloride. It is sparingly soluble in water. It was washed and dried as before. {Found : N, 35'18 ; F, 21'43 ; Ni, 13'37. $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_2\text{N}_6\text{H}_7)_2]\text{F}_2 \cdot \text{HF} \cdot (\text{NH}_4)\text{HF}_2 \cdot 3'5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires F, 21'65 ; N, 35'10 ; Ni, 13'38 per cent}.

Nickel bisbiguanidinium chlorate was obtained from a solution of the complex chloride and that of potassium chlorate. The deep yellow crystals were recrystallised from warm water and then washed and dried as

usual. {Found : Cl, 16.03; Ni, 13.10. $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_2\text{N}_3\text{H}_7)_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cl, 15.93; Ni, 13.17 per cent}.

Nickel bisbiguanidinium bromate was obtained in the form of deep yellow crystals from the complex chloride and potassium bromate and was purified by recrystallisation. {Found : Ni, 10.85; BrO_3 , 47.23. $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_2\text{N}_3\text{H}_7)_2](\text{BrO}_3)_2 \cdot 1.5 \text{ H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ni, 10.80; BrO_3 , 47.10 per cent}.

Nickel bisbiguanidinium iodate was obtained from a solution of the complex chloride and that of sodium iodate. The sparingly soluble, brownish yellow crystals were washed and dried as usual. {Found : Ni, 9.53; IO_3 , 56.65. $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_2\text{N}_3\text{H}_7)_2](\text{IO}_3)_2 \cdot 0.5 \text{ H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ni, 9.57; IO_3 , 56.45 per cent}.

Nickel bisbiguanidinium periodate was obtained as sparingly soluble, brownish yellow crystals by treating a solution of sodium periodate with that of the complex chloride. The composition corresponds to that of a meso-periodate. {Found : Ni, 13.20; IO_3 , 31.30. $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_2\text{N}_3\text{H}_7)_2]_3 \cdot (\text{IO}_3)_2 \cdot 7.5 \text{ H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ni, 13.23; IO_3 , 31.10 per cent}.

Nickel bisbiguanidinium perchlorate was prepared from a concentrated solution of sodium perchlorate and that of the complex chloride as needle-shaped, silky, yellow crystals. It was recrystallised from warm water, washed and dried as usual. {Found : Cl, 15.52; Ni, 12.75. $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_2\text{N}_3\text{H}_7)_2]_2 \cdot (\text{ClO}_4)_2$ requires Cl, 15.45; Ni, 12.76 per cent}.

Nickel bisbiguanidinium permanganate was obtained in the form of black, shining, needle-shaped crystals by adding a dilute solution of potassium permanganate to an excess of the concentrated solution of the complex chloride. The crystals were filtered through a sintered glass crucible, washed several times with ice-cold water and then dried on a porous plate. The substance is sparingly soluble in water and takes fire when treated with concentrated sulphuric acid. {Found : Ni, 11.88; MnO_4 , 47.31. $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_2\text{N}_3\text{H}_7)_2](\text{MnO}_4)_2$ requires Ni, 11.78; MnO_4 , 47.72 per cent}.

Nickel bisbiguanidinium borofluoride separated, on cooling a concentrated solution of the complex chloride mixed with that of ammonium borofluoride as yellow needle-shaped crystals. The crystals were filtered and recrystallised from warm water. They were then washed and dried as usual. {Found : Ni, 13.55. $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_2\text{N}_3\text{H}_7)_2](\text{BF}_4)_2$ requires Ni, 13.52 per cent}.

Nickel bisbiguanidinium nitrate was obtained in the form of sparingly soluble, woolly, reddish brown crystals by adding a solution of the complex chloride to that of potassium nitrate. The product was purified by recrystallisation. {Found : Ni, 14.56; NO_3 , 30.70. $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_2\text{N}_3\text{H}_7)_2](\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ni, 14.57; NO_3 , 30.73 per cent}.

Nickel bisbiguanidinium nitrite was isolated as sparingly soluble, brownish yellow crystals by treating a solution of the complex chloride with

that of potassium nitrite. It was purified by recrystallisation from warm water. {Found : Ni, 15'81; NO₂, 24'36. [Ni(C₂N₅H₇)₂](NO₂)₂.H₂O requires Ni, 15'83; NO₂, 24'82 per cent}.

Nickel bisbiguanidinium sulphate was obtained as a yellowish brown crystalline precipitate when a concentrated solution of the complex chloride was added to that of potassium sulphate. {Found : Ni, 14'25; SO₄, 23'48. [Ni(C₂N₅H₇)₂].SO₄.3H₂O requires Ni, 14'29; SO₄, 23'37 per cent}.

The same compound was also prepared by Stumpf (*loc. cit.*) by treating a solution of biguanide acid sulphate with that of nickel sulphate dissolved in ammonia.

Nickel bisbiguanidinium sulphite separated in the form of very sparingly soluble, yellowish brown crystals when a concentrated solution of the complex chloride was added to a freshly prepared solution of sodium sulphite. {Found : Ni, 14'85; SO₃, 20'36. [Ni(C₂N₅H₇)₂].SO₃.3H₂O requires Ni, 14'87; SO₃, 20'28 per cent}.

Nickel bisbiguanidinium thiosulphate was obtained from a concentrated solution of the complex chloride and that of sodium thiosulphate. The substance forms brownish yellow crystals and is almost insoluble in water. {Found : Ni, 14'30; S₂O₃, 27'40. [Ni(C₂N₅H₇)₂].S₂O₃.2H₂O requires Ni, 14'35; S₂O₃, 27'43 per cent}.

Nickel bisbiguanidinium dithionate was prepared from a concentrated solution of the complex chloride and that of sodium dithionate. The insoluble biscuit-coloured crystalline precipitate was washed and dried as usual. {Found : Ni, 12'87; S₂O₆, 34'89. [Ni(C₂N₅H₇)₂].S₂O₆.2H₂O requires Ni, 12'85; S₂O₆, 35'01 per cent}.

Nickel bisbiguanidinium thiocyanate was obtained as golden yellow crystals, moderately soluble in water, by mixing a concentrated solution of the complex chloride with that of ammonium thiocyanate. The product was purified by recrystallisation from warm water. {Found : Ni, 15'59; SCN, 30'86. [Ni(C₂N₅H₇)₂](SCN)₂ requires Ni, 15'58; SCN, 30'82 per cent}.

Nickel bisbiguanidinium selenate was obtained as biscuit-coloured crystalline precipitate by mixing solutions of ammonium selenate and the complex chloride {Found : Ni, 12'81; SeO₄, 31'13. [Ni(C₂N₅H₇)₂].SeO₄.3H₂O requires Ni, 12'81; SeO₄, 31'27 per cent}.

Nickel bisbiguanidinium chromate was obtained in the form of yellow, insoluble crystals by treating a solution of potassium chromate with that of the complex chloride. {Found : Ni, 13'54; CrO₄, 26'86. [Ni(C₂N₅H₇)₂].CrO₄.3H₂O requires Ni, 13'62; CrO₄, 26'94 per cent}.

Nickel bisbiguanidinium carbonate was precipitated in the form of orange-yellow crystals by adding a concentrated solution of the complex

chloride to that of sodium carbonate. {Found : C, 16.77 ; H, 5.10 ; Ni, 16.40. $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_2\text{N}_5\text{H}_7)_2]\text{CO}_3 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires C, 16.82 ; H, 5.05 ; Ni, 16.46 per cent}.

Nickel bisbiguanidinium ferrocyanide was obtained as a light yellow, insoluble precipitate by adding a concentrated solution of the complex chloride to that of potassium ferrocyanide. {Found : Fe, 7.0 ; Ni, 14.47. $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_2\text{N}_5\text{H}_7)_2]_2\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Fe, 6.94 ; Ni, 14.58 per cent}.

Nickel bisbiguanidinium ferricyanide was obtained from solutions of potassium ferricyanide and the complex chloride as a deep green, sparingly soluble, crystalline precipitate. {Found : Fe, 8.56 ; Ni, 13.47 $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_2\text{N}_5\text{H}_7)_2]_2[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6] \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Fe, 8.50 ; Ni, 13.40 per cent}.

Nickel bisbiguanidinium nitroprusside was isolated as moderately soluble, biscuit-coloured crystals by adding a solution of the complex chloride to that of an excess of sodium nitroprusside. {Found : Fe, 11.40 ; Ni, 11.91. $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_2\text{N}_5\text{H}_7)_2] \left[\text{Fe} \begin{array}{c} (\text{CN})_5 \\ (\text{NO}) \end{array} \right] \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Fe, 11.29 ; Ni, 11.87 per cent}.

Nickel bisbiguanidinium cobalticyanide was obtained from a solution of potassium cobalticyanide and that of the complex chloride as brownish yellow crystals, sparingly soluble in water. {Found : Co, 8.98 ; Ni, 13.29. $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_2\text{N}_5\text{H}_7)_2]_2[\text{Co}(\text{CN})_6] \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Co, 8.93 ; Ni, 13.34 per cent}.

Nickel bisbiguanidinium cobaltinitrite was prepared like the previous compound from a concentrated solution of sodium cobaltinitrite and that of the complex chloride, when an insoluble, deep yellow, crystalline precipitate was formed. {Found : Co, 6.69 ; Ni, 9.97. $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_2\text{N}_5\text{H}_7)_2]_2[\text{Co}(\text{NO})_6] \cdot 18\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Co, 6.64 ; Ni, 9.91 per cent}.

Nickel bisbiguanidinium mercuric iodide separated as a light yellow, crystalline precipitate, when a solution of potassium mercuric iodide was added to that of the complex chloride. {Found : I, 52.82 ; Hg, 20.88 ; Ni, 6.01. $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_2\text{N}_5\text{H}_7)_2]\text{HgI}_2$ requires I, 52.40 ; Hg, 20.70 ; Ni, 6.06 per cent}.

The unstable HgI_4^- ion, which exists only in solution in the case of potassium mercuric iodide, is here stabilised by combination with a complex cation of large volume. In the solid state potassium mercuric iodide has the composition KHgI_3 .

Nickel bisbiguanidinium Iodo-tri-iodide.—To an excess of a solution of iodine in potassium iodide, a solution of the complex chloride was added drop by drop. The brownish black, needle-shaped crystals of

the polyiodide separated out. These were filtered through a sintered glass crucible, washed several times with ice-cold water and dried on a porous plate for 4-6 hours.

The substance is difficultly soluble in water, but readily dissolves in alcohol, when freshly prepared. {Found : I (total), 63.53 ; I (associated), 32.0 ; Ni, 7.38. $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_2\text{N}_5\text{H}_7)_2] \frac{1}{\text{I}_3} \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires I (total), 63.83 ; I (associated), 31.91 ; Ni, 7.38 per cent.}

Nickel bisBiguanidinium Chloro-tri-iodide.—To a solution of potassium tri-iodide a concentrated solution of the complex chloride was added, drop by drop, the brownish black crystals of the complex iodo-tri-iodide, first precipitated, turned into dark green crystals with an excess of the complex chloride. The solution with the precipitate was allowed to remain for about half an hour. The crystals were then filtered through a sintered glass crucible, washed several times with a solution of the complex chloride and then finally with cold water. They were dried as in the previous case.

The compound forms dark green, needle-shaped crystals, difficultly soluble in water and insoluble in alcohol. It is converted into the brownish black crystals of the iodo-tri-iodide with an excess of potassium tri-iodide. {Found : Cl, 4.81 ; I (total), 52.04 ; I (associated), 34.58 ; Ni, 7.99. $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_2\text{N}_5\text{H}_7)_2] \frac{\text{Cl}}{\text{I}_3} \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cl, 4.86 ; I (total), 52.1 ; I (associated), 34.73 ; Ni, 8.03 per cent.}

On the addition of solutions of the following salts to a solution of the complex chloride, precipitates with characteristic colours were obtained.

Potassium Bismuthi-iodide, KBiI_4 .—Crimson-coloured, crystalline product, soluble in alcohol, but readily hydrolysed by water. With excess of the complex chloride an orange yellow compound with chlorine in the anion was formed. This is insoluble in alcohol, but readily hydrolysed in water.

Potassium Chromithiocyanate, $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}(\text{SCN})_6$.—Bluish violet, insoluble precipitate. With an excess of the complex chloride the colour changes to light violet and contains chlorine in the anion.

Sodium platinichloride, as well as the aurichloride, give yellow, insoluble, crystalline precipitates.